

The Tourist Satisfaction on Brand Identity Design of Creative Agriculture Community Enterprise, Bang Khonthi District, Samut Songkhram Province

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Abstract—The aims of this research were twofold: 1) to brand identity design of Creative Agriculture Community Enterprise, Bang Khonthi District, Samut Songkhram Province and 2) to study the level of tourist satisfaction towards brand identity design of Creative Agriculture Community Enterprise, Bang Khonthi District, Samut Songkhram Province. tourist satisfaction was measured using six criteria: clear brand positioning, likeable brand personality, memorable logo, attractive color palette, professional typography and on-brand supporting graphics. The researcher utilized a probability sampling method via simple random sampling. The sample consisted of 30 tourists in the Creative Agriculture Community Enterprise. Statistics utilized for data analysis were percentage, mean, and standard deviation. The results suggest that tourist had high levels of satisfaction towards all six criteria of the brand identity design that was designed to target them. This study proposes that specifically brand identity designed of Creative Agriculture Community Enterprise could also be implemented with other real media already available on the market.

Keywords—Satisfaction, brand identity, logo, creative agriculture community enterprise

I. INTRODUCTION

TO start up a business nowadays, no matter whether to serve commercial purposes or the small or big government sector purposes, it was essential to have a distinctive logo in order to communicate personal brand identity, establish trust, build organizational identity, as well as be recalled in the consumers' minds over the long terms. Due to these reasons, easier and more effective public communication was emerged. Brand Identity, playing a significant role in sending out messages to the target audience, was like the image of the business or the goods.

Brand identity is the face of a brand. Brand Identity was originated by an artistic thinking process integrated with a well-designed communication process by focusing on the uniqueness of the object and presenting it to the publics to create better awareness. Brand identity includes logos, typography, colors, packaging, messaging, and personality all represent a brand, along with customer service [1]. A good logo was able to communicate itself the target market functionally, and get remembered without using striking colors. Making decisions in the selection of typefaces and deal with the application of typefaces to the brand identity design process [2], additionally,

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was able to communicate well regardless of its size and could be used with variety of media including billboards for advertising and public relations, packaging, business cards, document, and printed material as well as websites, etc. Brand Identity was therefore a crucial part in doing businesses and activities as it helped to send messages out to the target market efficiently. Brand Identity Design an important role in every department and/or organization to consumers in spite of intense materialistic competitiveness in today world. A Brand Identity is the set for a consumer's decision to choose one product or service over another.

Creative Agriculture Community Enterprise, Bang Khonthi District, Samut Songkhram Province and the vicinity areas. Local income distribution happened here since the local brought their products from their farms to sell at this Creative Agriculture Community Enterprise directly to tourists. On top of mushroom which were popular at this market, this was being said that this community enterprise was a center of souvenirs and OTOP products in Samut Songkhram Province as well as a rest area for Bangkok tourists to drop by for enjoyable shopping.

Nonetheless, there was no Brand Identity to represent Creative Agriculture Community Enterprise yet. Brand Identity could be used as a brand representative to convey messages to the publics in various forms like labels, packaging, name cards, document, print media, and website. This would bring about huge benefits to merchants in the community enterprise [3].

As things go, the researcher was into designing and developing a Brand Identity for the community enterprise in order to add value, establish its identity and trust, along with get tourists remember this market after their visit over a long period of time.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A logo design was an artistic process starting from setting a format, definition, appearance, and image by paying particular attention to the unique selling point to present and explain its definition including who, what, how and when to the publics to perceive easily. A designer had to utilize his capability and knowledge in doing analysis on the core messages to be transmitted as they were entitled to give definition about the object to the target group.

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The principle of logo design comprised 1) simplicity to understand, perceive, and remember 2) memorableness of logo for the brand it represented 3) timelessness to brand attached over the next 10, 20, or 50 years 4) versatility for various media used 5) appropriation to the target group due to good logo positioning [4].

Color psychology lead a person to pay attention to the main content. In comparison to shape, color was more virtual to images and more effective to critical points in the pictures. Hence, fitting good color tone was extremely important. 1) Red was the most striking and the most powerful among the warm colors. It gave confidence, motivation, enthusiasm, excitement, and strength. It was usually coupled with intriguing objects or boards 2) Orange stood in for agility, merry, warmth, chill-out atmosphere 3) Yellow created inspiration, happiness, warmth, eagerness, and excitement. 4) Green indicated peace, freshness, youth, and it was used to represent balance, harmony, security, perseverance, and fertility. 5) Blue illustrated trust, honesty, and determination. It also appeared for calmness and spirit. Dark blue was suitable for business/organizational design aimed to show high-end technology, to give a feeling of future. Additionally, blue used for social media symbolized wisdom and warmth. 6) Purple signified respectability and dignity. It was connected to creativity. Dark purple acted as magnificence and wealth. Light purple meant spring season and romance. 7) Black expressed power, charm, stylishness, and mystery. 8) Gray embodied peace and justice. The designed work in gray color was perceived as conservative but lack of energy. 9) White stood for clarification, cleanliness, open mind, and simplicity. 10) Brown was typically part of the surface often used as a background color. In addition, it represented peace, elegance, and pureness while giving a feeling of conservatism and faith.

Key design elements need to create a brand identity that is strong, consistent, and attractive.

1) Clear brand objective and key message is the first part of establishing a brand identity. Defining these will inform your strategy as you create a brand logo. A process called Design Objective, Positioning and Key message is useful for answering these questions. 2) Market research can also help you determine who your main customer personas are. Government resources also be a powerful tool, along with online survey tools are a fast way to gather a lot of information. Simply talk to people is the best ways to conduct market research. 3) Brand personality, the question "If your brand were a person, what would they be like?" it's a smart way to think about brand personality. Brand personality has an impact on the mood and tone in your marketing communications [5]. If a personality isn't established, customers have trouble connecting with your brand. 4) Memorable logo. A simplicity of brand logo is crucial, the concept of the logo focused on being easily readable for a simplicity to understand and remember [6]. The customer has a positive feeling with the brand when a logo is simple. The final thinking when designing a brand logo is the versatility for use. A brand logo needs to be flexible enough to look great on a Printed Advertising or as a social media. Simplicity is helpful to memorable logo. 5) Brand color palette should have only a few primary colors. decide on a brand color palette with printed

process color mode (CMYK, Pantone) and multimedia color mode (RGB) 6) Brand typeface. typeface are powerful. the best ways to conduct pick a font that works in harmony with your brand logo. You'll want a single primary typeface to lead your brand identity design, 7) Supporting graphics. visual language is the final step in creating a brand identity with supporting graphics, icons, symbols, illustration and photographs [1].

III. METHODOLOGY

This research was an experimental research. It was conducted based on a one-shot case study design which aimed to test with one experimental group. The researcher executed the study as well as collected data in order as pointed out below.

A. Period 1: Study Initial Information Used to Brand Identity Design

A field study to collect data from the merchants in the Creative Agriculture Community Enterprise and consumers was conducted so as to use the obtained data to design a brand identity for the market. There were 2 types of data collection as follows;

1. Primary data: this included background and history of the Creative Agriculture Community Enterprise. In order to such information, the interview on the village headman, the merchants in the community enterprise as well as those local living nearby was carried out. In the present, Thai consumers are more complicated. There is a wide gap in age, gender, occupation, social class, lifestyle, culture and religion [7]. Behavioral observations on buyers and sellers were performed together with the use of questionnaire to capture basic information for a brand identity design.
2. Secondary data: the data were collected from essential and relating document.

B. Period 2: Design a Logo

The following techniques were employed;

- Locate a logo symbolized the expected benefits.
- Use a pencil to draft various ideas.
- Select the best 3 ideas for preliminary artwork design.
- Select the font characterized per the expectation.
- Select the color set following the emotion and the feeling to be built.
- Conduct an opinion survey from involving people along with those who were not aware of the local products. Then evaluate which idea created best potential result.
- Compare pros and cons of each idea, consult logo design specialists to later modify the contents as well as adjust the required portions based on the advice from the specialist.
- Fine-tune the content to become flawless and change the necessary parts based on the specialists' advice.
- Make a brand identity manual containing how to use a logo, font name, graphic and color palette along with a template.

C. Period 3: Conduct an Assessment by a Specialist

An assessment form was established by the researcher and used by the 5 appointed specialists to measure the quality of the designed brand identity for further improvement.

D. Period 4: Measure Tourists' Satisfaction on the Brand Identity Used for Creative Agriculture Community Enterprise

The measurement form was created by dividing into 6 different aspects 1) clear brand positioning 2) likeable brand personality 3) memorable logo 4) attractive color palette 5) professional typography 6) on-brand supporting graphics. Once the assessment was completed, the researcher statistically analyzed the result for conclusion and presentation.

IV. FINDINGS/RESULTS

The research with the topic of the Tourists' satisfaction on brand identity design of Creative Agriculture Community Enterprise, Bang Khonthi District, Samut Songkhram Province was conducted on 30 samples. The research results were examined and presented in a form of explanation table. Brand identity design satisfaction was scored in general as follows;

TABLE I
 ASSESSMENT RESULT OF TOURISTS' SATISFACTION ON BRAND IDENTITY DESIGN OF CREATIVE AGRICULTURE COMMUNITY ENTERPRISE BANG KHONTHI DISTRICT, SAMUT SONGKHRAM PROVINCE

Satisfaction Measurement	$\bar{X}$	S.D.	Satisfaction Level
Clear brand positioning	4.49	0.62	High
Likeable brand personality	4.53	0.67	Highest
Memorable logo	4.65	0.68	Highest
Attractive color palette	4.47	0.77	High
Professional typography	4.48	0.60	High
On-brand supporting graphics	4.37	0.89	High
Average score	4.49	0.72	High

From the Table I, it was found that the satisfaction levels on the 6 aspects were at the highest ($\bar{X} = 4.49$). Memorable logo ($\bar{X} = 4.65$) were the highest level of satisfaction. Yet, On-brand supporting graphics was at the least satisfaction level ($\bar{X} = 4.37$).

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This research was intended to 1) design a brand identity for Creative Agriculture Community Enterprise, Bang Khonthi District, Samut Songkhram Province and 2) to evaluate the tourists' satisfaction towards the brand identity design.

There were 4 periods in this study;

- *Period 1:* Study the initial information useful for a brand identity design. The researcher collected the data by visiting and interviewing village headman, the merchants, and the local dweller to obtain background and history of the community enterprise. Behavioral observation on the merchants and the buyers was performed; moreover, a questionnaire to get initial information beneficial for the brand identity design was executed. Besides, the study on relevant documents was carried out at this stage as well.
- *Period 2:* Design the logo. This was started out by locating the symbol that could convey the expected benefits, sketching variety of possible ideas and picking on the best 3 solutions for a preliminary artwork design. Font selection by choosing the one with the wanted character, color set

selection that could appealed the desired emotion and feelings were initiated at this stage. Once all of the designs based on the top 3 ideas were completed, they were compared with one another in terms of pros and cons. Consultancy with specialists for improvement were carried out in order to allow the researcher to adjust and modify the design as appropriate. Lastly, the document illustrating how to use the logo, the font name, the color palette and graphic as well as a template used was made.

- *Period 3:* Evaluate brand identity design quality by 5 specialists by using the assessment form made by the researcher. Improvement and adjustment to the branding was made at this stage based on the specialists' advice.
- *Period 4:* Measure the tourists' satisfaction on brand identity design by segregating into 6 aspects including 1) clear brand positioning 2) likeable brand personality 3) memorable logo 4) attractive color palette 5) professional typography and 6) on-brand supporting graphics. Once the evaluation was completed, the result was scrutinized statistically for conclusion and presentation at the next step.

From the study, it was concluded that the overall satisfaction level to brand identity design was at the high level ($\bar{X} = 4.49$) which was in accordance with the research hypothesis. In terms of the memorable logo, it was at the maximum satisfaction. Simplicity signified ease and flexibility of the logo that it could be used with other media efficiently. Also, it meant that the logo was easy to recognized. However, behind the simplicity, the designer had to put a lot of thinking efforts and draft various potential concepts in order to generate the logo that functioned so superbly that the viewers could easily notice and recall it [8].

VI. SUGGESTIONS

Designing an adept logo required skills and capabilities in a designer like the ability to use various design tools including pen, pencil, assorted colors as well as a computer to transform concepts into images. Additionally, the designer was supposed to pay attention to changes around the world that happened unceasingly particularly on the markets and the mass communication. He had to own visions that could foresee a potential future as one single logo was supposed to live long [9].

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